

Participant Follow-up CRF

#	Question	Variable
1	Today's date	DD/MM/YYYY
2	Household ID	
3	Enter the participant ID.	
Section 1: Travel and Work		
4	Have you travelled outside of the country since the last visit?	Yes No (go to Q5)
4a	Where did you travel to?	
4b	What was the purpose of this travel?	For work Visiting family or friends Holiday For healthcare Other (specify)
4c	Have you travelled anywhere else outside of the country since the last visit?	Yes No (go to Q5)
4d	Where did you travel to?	
4e	What was the purpose of this travel?	For work Visiting family or friends Holiday For healthcare Other (specify)
5	Have you travelled outside of Blantyre / Chikwawa / Hoima / Kampala since our last visit?	Yes No (go to Q6)
5a	Where did you travel to?	
5b	What was the purpose of this travel?	For work (go to Q6) Visiting family or friends (go to Q6) Holiday (go to Q6) For healthcare Other (specify) (go to Q6)
5c	If you seek healthcare, what type of facility was this?	Tertiary Referral Hospital Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store

		Traditional medical house CHAM facility Other (specify)
5d	What were you treated for?	Fever Diarrhoea Cough/cold Sore throat Skin infection Urinary Tract Infection / dysuria Malaria (RDT confirmed only) TB (Confirmed /presumed) Brain infection (Meningitis / encephalitis) Blood stream infection Other infection (specify) Non-infectious cause (specify)
5e	Did you receive any antibiotics?	Yes No (go to Q6)
5ei	What antibiotics did you receive? (Tick all)	Amoxicillin Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid Ampicillin Ampicillin + Cloxacillin Azithromycin Benzathine benzylpenicillin Benzylpenicillin Cefalexin/Cephalexin Cefixime Ceftriaxone Cefuroxime Chloramphenicol Ciprofloxacin Clarithromycin Clindamycin Cloxacillin Cotrimoxazole (Sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim) Doxycycline Erythromycin Flucloxacillin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Metronidazole Ofloxacin Phenoxymethylpenicillin Tetracycline Tinidazole Other (specify) Unknown

5eii	What form was the antibiotic? (Tick for each antibiotic)	PO (oral) PR (rectal) SL (under the tongue) IV (intravenous) IM (injection into the muscle) S/C (injection under the skin)
6	Have you started a new job since the last visit?	Yes No (go to Q7)
6a	What job have you started	Agriculture Domestic Service Unskilled manual Skilled manual Sales and services Clerical Technical / managerial Healthcare Other professional Student Other (please specify)
7	Have you worked in a school since our last visit?	Yes No (go to Q8)
7a	What type of school?	Primary Secondary College University Other (specify)
7b	What is the name of the school that you work in?	
7c	What is your job at the school?	Teacher Teaching Assistant Other (specify)
8	Have you worked in a health care since our last visit?	Yes No (go to Q9)
8a	What type of place?	Tertiary Referral Hospital Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house CHAM facility Other (specify)
8b	Where do you work? (name of the healthcare institution)	
8c	What is your job at this health care institution?	Doctor Nurse

		Cleaner Other (specify)
Section 2: Health Facility Exposure		
9	Since our last visit have you stayed overnight in Hospital as a guardian?"	Yes No (go to Q10)
9a	When were you in hospital as a guardian?	DD/MM/YYYY
9b	Where were you in hospital as a guardian?	
9c	How long were you a guardian in the hospital for?	1 day 2 days 3 days 4 days 5 days 6 days 7 days 7-14 days >14 days
10	Since our last visit have you been admitted to hospital (for at least one night)?	Yes No (go to Q11)
10a	When was this?	DD/MM/YYYY
10b	Where was this?	
10c	What were you treated for?	Fever Diarrhoea Cough/cold Sore throat Skin infection Urinary Tract Infection / dysuria Malaria (RDT confirmed only) TB (Confirmed /presumed) Brain infection (Meningitis / encephalitis) Blood stream infection Other infection (specify) Non-infectious cause (specify)
10d	How long did you stay at hospital?	1 day 2 days 3 days 4 days 5 days 6 days 7 days 7-14 days >14 days
10e	Were you given antibiotics?	Yes

		No (go to Q11)
10ei	What antibiotics did you receive? (Tick all)	Amoxicillin Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid Ampicillin Ampicillin + Cloxacillin Azithromycin Benzathine benzylpenicillin Benzylpenicillin Cefalexin/Cephalexin Cefixime Ceftriaxone Cefuroxime Chloramphenicol Ciprofloxacin Clarithromycin Clindamycin Cloxacillin Cotrimoxazole (Sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim) Doxycycline Erythromycin Flucloxacillin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Metronidazole Ofloxacin Phenoxymethylpenicillin Tetracycline Tinidazole Other (specify) Unknown
10eii	What form was the antibiotic? (Tick for each antibiotic)	PO (oral) PR (rectal) SL (under the tongue) IV (intravenous) IM (injection into the muscle) S/C (injection under the skin)
Section 3: HIV Status		
11	Any new HIV diagnosis since our last visit?	Yes No (go to Q12)
11a	Source of HIV status?	Participant Record card Other (specify)
11b	Date of HIV test?	DD/MM/YYYY
11c	Is the CD4 count known?	Yes

		No (go to 28d)
11ci	CD4 source?	Participant Record card Other (specify)
11cii	CD4 count (cells/mm ³)	
11ciii	CD4 date?	DD/MM/YYYY
11d	Is the Last viral load known?	Yes No (go to 28e)
11di	Viral load source?	Participant Record card Other (specify)
11dii	Last viral load (copies/ml)	
11diii	Viral Load date?	DD/MM/YYYY
11e	Under HIV follow up?	Yes No (go to 28f)
11ei	Where?	
11f	On ART?	Yes No (go to Q28h)
11fi	ART start date?	DD/MM/YYYY
11fii	ART current regimen? Select if adult or child.	1 (D4T/3TC/NVP) 2 (AZT/3TC/NVP) 3 (D4T/3TC/NVP) 4 (AZT/3TC/EFV) 5 (TDF/3TC/EFV) 6 (TDF/3TC/NVP) 7 (TDF/3TC/LPVr) 8 (AZT/3TC/LPVr) 9 (ABC/3TC/LPVr) 13a (TDF/3TC/Dolutegravir) Other combination (go to Qfiii)
11fiii	Other regimen (tick all that apply)	NVP (Nevirapine) EFV (Efavirenz) LPV/r (Lopinavir/ritonavir) ATV/r (Atazanavir/ritonavir) 3TC (Lamivudine) AZT ABC (Abacavir) FTC (Emtricitabine) D4T TDF (Tenofovir) Dolutegravir Other (specify)
11g	On Cotrimoxazole Preventative Therapy (CPT)	Yes No (go to Q29)
11gi	CPT start date	DD/MM/YYYY

Section 4: Medication Changes		
12	Any new medications, including HIV medications (other than antibiotics) since our last visit?	Yes No (go to Q13)
12a	Medication name	
12b	Start Date	DD/MM/YYYY
12c	Dose (mg)	
12d	Route	PO (oral) PR (rectal) SL (under the tongue) IV (intravenous) IM (injection into the muscle) S/C (injection under the skin)
12e	Dose frequency	OD (once a day) BD (twice a day) TDS (3 times a day) QDS (4 times a day) Other (specify)
12f	Medication ongoing	Yes (go to Q30h) No
12g	End date	DD/MM/YYYY
12h	Are they on any other medication?	Yes (<u>repeat Q12 for each new medication</u>) No
Section 5: Health Questions and Interim Antibiotic Use		
13	Have you been unwell SINCE OUR LAST VISIT? (other than the time you were admitted to hospital – if applicable)	Yes No (go to Q14)
13a	What with?	Fever Diarrhoea Cough/cold Sore throat Skin infection Urinary Tract Infection / dysuria Malaria (RDT confirmed only) TB (Confirmed /presumed) Brain infection (Meningitis / encephalitis) Blood stream infection Other infection (specify) Non-infectious cause (specify)
13b	Did you receive antibiotics for this?	Yes No (go to Q14)

Now I would like to ask you about the antibiotics you took.		
13bi	Which antibiotic was it? (complete Q13bii-13bvi for each antibiotic selected)	Amoxicillin Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid Ampicillin Ampicillin + Cloxacillin Azithromycin Benzathine benzylpenicillin Benzylpenicillin Cefalexin/Cephalexin Cefixime Ceftriaxone Cefuroxime Chloramphenicol Ciprofloxacin Clarithromycin Clindamycin Cloxacillin Cotrimoxazole (Sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim) Doxycycline Erythromycin Flucloxacillin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Metronidazole Ofloxacin Phenoxyethylpenicillin Tetracycline Tinidazole Other (specify) Unknown
13bii	What form was the antibiotic	PO (oral) PR (rectal) SL (under the tongue) IV (intravenous) IM (injection into the muscle) S/C (injection under the skin)
13biii	What dose did you take (mg)?	
13biv	How long did you take it for?	As advised Until cured Until package empty As long as I could afford to One-time treatment Continuously over extended period
13bv	Where did you get the antibiotic from?	Drug shop Traditional healer Pharmacy

		Referral hospital Other Public Health Facility Private clinic Research clinic/NGO Private hospital Family/friends Other (specify)
13bvi	Why did you get it from here?	Cost Location Availability of drugs Recommended by doctor Other (specify)
Section 6: Current Antibiotic Use		
14	Are you on antibiotics at the moment, that have not been captured already?	Yes No (go to Q15)
14a	Which antibiotics is it? (complete Q14ai-14av for each antibiotic selected)	Amoxicillin Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid Ampicillin Ampicillin + Cloxacillin Azithromycin Benzathine benzylpenicillin Benzylpenicillin Cefalexin/Cephalexin Cefixime Ceftriaxone Cefuroxime Chloramphenicol Ciprofloxacin Clarithromycin Clindamycin Cloxacillin Cotrimoxazole (Sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim) Doxycycline Erythromycin Flucloxacillin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Metronidazole Ofloxacin Phenoxymethylpenicillin Tetracycline Tinidazole Other (specify) Unknown

14ai	What form is the antibiotic	PO (oral) PR (rectal) SL (under the tongue) IV (intravenous) IM (injection into the muscle) S/C (injection under the skin)
14aii	What dose are you taking (mg)?	
14aiii	What are you taking it for?	Fever Diarrhoea Cough/cold Sore throat Skin infection Urinary Tract Infection / dysuria Malaria (RDT confirmed only) TB (Confirmed /presumed) Brain infection (Meningitis / encephalitis) Blood stream infection Other infection (specify) Non-infectious cause (specify)
14aiv	Why did you get it from here?	Cost Location Availability of drugs Recommended by doctor Other (specify)
14av	Why did you get it from here?	Cost Location Availability of drugs Recommended by doctor Other (specify)
15	You have completed data collection for this participant. Please thank them for their time.	
16	Staff signature	
17	Time and Date	MM:HH DD/MM/YYYY